

DYNAMIC STRESS–STRAIN RELATIONSHIP OF ALUMINUM POWDERS USING MULTI-PARTICLE FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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Keywords: granular metal materials, shock compression, multi-particle finite element methods, shock model, dynamic stress–strain relationship

ABSTRACT

The dynamic compression behavior of particulate metal materials has not been fully understood. In this study, based on the multi-particle finite element methods, a two-dimensional numerical analysis model of granular metal materials was established, and the mechanical behaviors of aluminum powders under constant-velocity compression were studied. The numerical results show that the granular metal materials exhibit a highly localized deformation band under high-velocity impact (175~300 m/s), and the deformation bands propagate from the impact end to the support end like a shock wave. By using the velocity field calculation method, the position of the plastic impact wave front was calculated, and the Hugoniot relation between the impact velocity and the shock velocity of aluminum powders with different relative densities (0.45~0.65) was obtained. It is found the shock wave velocity varies linearly with the impact velocity. The dynamic stress–strain states behind the shock front were obtained based on the plastic shock model. The dynamic stress–strain relationship was determined by using the shock wave model with the implement of a linear relation between the shock velocity and the impact velocity. The proposed dynamic stress–strain relation can provide useful data to solve dynamic loading problems in which granular metals are utilized.

1 INTRODUCTION

Granular metal materials have been widely used in many industrial fields, such as aerospace, metallurgy and electronics, due to their advantageous properties of multi-scale, porosity, fluidity and strength [1-3]. The rapid compaction of granular metal materials is of great interest in industrial manufacturing [4], but the densification process is still lack of a continuum representation and the dynamic compression behaviors of metal powders need deep researches.

To understand the bulk response of a rapidly compacted granular metal material, a series of methods have been developed. Experimental tests are usually applied to measure the initial and final states of materials under impact [5-6]. Numerical simulation, such as Eulerian hydrocodes [7] and discrete element methods [8] can help to understand the process of densification and have been successfully used to estimate the bulk materials properties of granular system, such as Hugoniot slope, compaction density, energy deposition and zero pressure shock speed [7-10]. However, Eulerian hydrocode may describe the high-velocity region well but be limited in characterizing the low-velocity compression behaviors [7]. Discrete element methods may be unsuitable on the compaction stage due to the simplification of particle contact formulation [8, 11]. Multi-particle finite element methods (MPFEM) may be applied to solve these issues. In previous studies, multi-particle finite element methods have been adopted to study the quasi-static compaction behaviors of powders [12-14]. Recently, we have applied a multi-particle finite element method to understand the dynamic compression behaviors with predicting the Hugoniot relation of copper powders at medium velocities (200~300 m/s) and developed a shock wave model with using the dynamic locking strain as the only parameter [15]. However, the shock wave model is applicable when the strain behind the shock front approaches to the theoretical maximum compaction strain. To better understand the mechanical behaviors behind the shock front, a more accurate model is required.

In this study, a 2D multi-particle finite element method was applied to simulate the dynamic compression behaviors of granular metal materials. Aluminum powders with the strength that is comparable to the induced shock stress were selected as the research object. The deformation feature and particle velocity distribution under constant-velocity loading were explored. The relationship between the shock velocity and the particle velocity was established. Furthermore, the dynamic stress–strain states behind the shock front were obtained and then the dynamic stress–strain relationship was determined.

2 NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

Multi-particle finite element method was employed in this study. In this method, initial geometrical models were constructed randomly and then the finite element models were generated. Each particle was meshed with using finite element code ABAQUS/Explicit 6.11. The geometrical model of powder was constructed by a random scattered technique with the assumption that each particle is circle and equal-diameter. The scattering rules could be briefly introduced as below: placing particles in a square box and making sure there is no overlap until reaching the pre-determined initial relative density, as done in Ref. [15]. The initial relative density ρ is defined as Ω_0/Ω_f with Ω_0 and Ω_f being the volume of the powders and the volume of the square box, respectively. The diameter of each particle is set as 30 μm . According to the convergence analysis of mesh, each particle is divided into 100 hexahedral elements (C3D8R) with 226 nodes, as shown in Fig. 1(b). The thickness of elements in the out-of-plane direction is taken to be 3 μm . All nodes of powder are constrained in the out-of-plane direction to simulate a plane strain state. The material of Al powder is assumed to be elastic, perfectly plastic with density 2700 kg/m^3 , Young's modulus 69 GPa, Poisson's ratio 0.34 and yield stress 265 MPa. General contact with friction coefficient 0.2 between particles is defined in simulations.

A constant-velocity compression loading system was considered in this study, as shown in Fig. 1(a). The powder specimens are confined in a rigid square die. The dimensions of the square die are 1 mm \times 1 mm. The walls of the die are fixed except the loading end. A velocity boundary condition was imposed via the rigid plate at the loading end, which moves with a constant velocity V towards the support end.

Figure 1: (a) A multi-particle finite element model and (b) the initial mesh of a particle.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Deformation and particle velocity

The deformation patterns of a sample with an initial relative density of 0.65 under compression

velocity 300 m/s are shown in Fig. 2. As can be seen, particulate metal materials exhibit highly localized deformation feature under dynamic impact, which is consistent with Ref. [15]. Stress wave propagates forward along the loading direction in the form of shock wave. The width of the wave front is about 2 to 4 particle diameters. One-dimensional velocity field calculation method is introduced to quantitatively characterize the propagation characteristics of shock wave. The velocity components of each node in the loading direction are averaged to obtain the velocity distribution of Al powder at different times, as shown in Fig. 3. The velocity field can well capture the deformation feature of Al powder under high-velocity impact, indicating that the rapid change of velocity is concentrated in a narrow area. Considering 200 m/s compression scenario, it is found that the higher the impact velocity, the narrower the area is.

Figure 2: Deformation patterns at different times under compression velocity 300 m/s.

Figure 3: Particle velocity distribution under compression velocities of (a) 200 m/s and (b) 300 m/s.

3.2 Shock velocity

The shock velocity (V_s) and the particle velocity are calculated to characterize the Hugoniot relations of Al powders. Based on the above analysis, the velocity distribution of Al powder under high-velocity compression can be divided into three regions: the undeformed zone ahead of the shock front, the compacted zone behind the shock front and the region where the state changes abruptly. By calculating the velocity gradient, the change degree of velocity was obtained. From Fig. 4(a), there is a minimum value of velocity gradient, indicating the velocity varies most dramatically in this position. Here, this position is taken as the position of the shock front at this moment. As shown in Fig. 4(b), the position of shock front is approximately linear with time, so the shock velocity can be obtained through linear fitting. And by this method, the shock velocities of Al powders with different initial

relative densities under different impact velocities are also calculated. The V_s - V relationships with relative densities of 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, 0.60 and 0.65 are shown in Fig. 5. The results indicate a linear relation between the shock velocity and the particle velocity, which is expressed as

$$V_s = kV + c, \quad (1)$$

where k is the slope of the V_s - V and c is the ordinate at the origin. Here, for Al powders with relative densities of 0.45, 0.50, 0.55, 0.60 and 0.65, the values of k are 1.58, 1.69, 1.79, 1.93 and 2.08, respectively, and the values of c are 89, 101, 128, 173 and 219 m/s, respectively.

Figure 4: (a) One-dimensional velocity distribution and the corresponding velocity gradient and (b) variation of shock front position with impact time under impact velocities of 200 and 300 m/s.

Figure 5: Variation of shock velocity with the particle velocity at different initial relative densities of Al powders.

4 THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Under uniaxial impact compression, the stress wave propagates from the loading end to the support end in the form of one-dimensional strain plane wave, so the analysis of impact compression of powder can be simplified to a one-dimensional model. One-dimensional shock wave theory gives the conservation relations of mass and momentum in the forms of

$$v_B - v_A = V_s(\varepsilon_B - \varepsilon_A), \quad (2)$$

and

$$\sigma_B - \sigma_A = \rho_0 V_s (v_B - v_A), \quad (3)$$

respectively [16], where ρ_0 is the initial density of Al powders, $\{v_A, \varepsilon_A, \sigma_A\}$ and $\{v_B, \varepsilon_B, \sigma_B\}$ are velocity, strain and stress states ahead of and behind the shock wave front, respectively. It is noted that the elastic wave cannot propagate forward in unjammed granular materials due to the loose packing structure and inter-particle void. Therefore, the stress, strain and velocity ahead of the shock front are assumed to be zero, i.e. $v_A = 0$, $\varepsilon_A = 0$ and $\sigma_A = 0$, independent of the loading velocity. Besides, the velocity behind the shock front under constant-velocity compression approaches V , i.e. $v_B = V$. Thus, the shock velocity in Eq. (2) and the stress after shock wave in Eq. (3) can be rewritten as

$$V_s = V / \varepsilon_B, \quad (4)$$

and

$$\sigma_B = \rho_0 V^2 / \varepsilon_B, \quad (5)$$

respectively. According to the shock velocity of finite element results, the dynamic stress–strain states behind the shock front can be calculated with Eqs. (4) and (5) and the results were shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Dynamic stress–strain states behind the shock front at different initial relative densities of Al powders.

Initial relative density, ρ	Maximal consolidation strain, ε_m	Strain hardening parameter, D (MPa)
0.45	0.64	4.3
0.50	0.60	5.3
0.55	0.56	8.3
0.60	0.52	14.0
0.65	0.48	19.4

Table 1: The values of ε_m and D for powders with different initial relative densities.

Based on the analysis in section 3.2, implementing the linear Hugoniot relationship Eq. (1) into Eq. (5), we have

$$\sigma = \frac{D\varepsilon}{(\varepsilon_m - \varepsilon)^2}, \quad (6)$$

where $\varepsilon_m = k^{-1}$ is defined as the maximal consolidation strain and $D = \rho_0 c^2 / k^2$ is an empirical fitting parameter, which characterizes strain hardening behavior of powder. Therefore, the dynamic stress–strain relationship of Al powders was obtained. The form of this relationship is simple, which is explicit and only contains two parameters. In this study, the values of ε_m and D for powders with

different initial relative densities are listed in Table 1, which are calculated based on the values of k and c in section 3.2. Then, the stress–strain curves could be determined by Eq. (6) and are shown in Fig. 6.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The process of shock compression of Al powder was simulated by using multi-particle element method. The particle deformation and particle velocity of Al powder under constant-velocity compression were studied. The velocity field calculation method was employed to calculate the particle velocity distribution and the position of plastic shock wave front and then to determine the shock velocity. The numerical results show that a highly localized deformation band under high-velocity impact (175~300 m/s) was observed, and the deformation band propagates like a plain shock wave. The position of shock front is approximately linear with time. The shock velocity varies linearly with the particle velocity of Al powders with different relative densities (0.45~0.65). Based on the linear V_s - V relationship of granular materials, the dynamic stress–strain relationship was determined. Further work may focus on the experimental verification of the dynamic constitutive relationship of powder.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is supported by the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (Grant No. WK2480000003).

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